

Range reshuffling: climate change, invasive species, and the case of Nothofagus forests in Aotearoa New Zealand

– ODMAP Protocol –

Shar Mathias, Laura van Galen, Scott Jarvie, Matthew Larcombe

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Overview

Authorship

Contact : laura.vangalen9@gmail.com

Study link: DOI will be provided once assigned

Model objective

Model objective: Forecast and transfer

Target output: Predicting suitable habitat under future climate scenarios for native Nothofagus and introduced conifer species in New Zealand

Focal Taxon

Focal Taxon: Nothofagus (Nothofagaceae) and conifer (Pinaceae) species

Location

Location: New Zealand

Scale of Analysis

Spatial extent: 166, 179, -48, -34.5 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 1 km

Temporal extent: Current climate (average of 1981-2010) and future climate (average of 2041-2070) scenarios

Temporal resolution: Current (2010) and future (2070); see above

Boundary: natural

Biodiversity data

Observation type: field survey, standardised monitoring data

Response data type: presence-only

Predictors

Predictor types: climatic, edaphic

Hypotheses

Hypotheses: That the distribution of environmentally suitable habitat area will change for both native *Nothofagus* and invasive conifer species in the future, leading to potential competition between native and invasive species for newly suitable habitat area

Assumptions

Model assumptions: That species' occurrence records accurately reflect their current distributions, and that these distributions are at equilibrium with the environment

Algorithms

Modelling techniques: maxent

Model complexity: We used settings likely to be more reliable for model transfer (regularisation multiplier = 2, feature class = hinge)

Model averaging: No

Workflow

Model workflow: 1) Downloaded, cleaned, and filtered occurrence records; 2) Fitted maxent models (R package 'maxnet' version 0.1.4); 3) Calculated probability of environmentally suitable habitat for current and future climates ("predict" function); 4) Evaluated model performance using the "ENMeval" package version 2.0.1

Software

Software: R version 4.2.1. Key packages: "maxnet" version 0.1.4; "raster" version 3.5 ; "galah" version 1.5.0; "rgbif" version 3.7.3 ; "CoordinateCleaner" version 2.0-20 ; "flexsdm" version 1.3.2; "ENMeval" version 2.0.1; "dismo" version 1.3-9; "SpatialRF" version 1.1.4

Code availability: Code is provided as Supporting Information

Data availability: All data are provided as Supporting Information

Data

Biodiversity data

Taxon names: *Nothofagus cliffortioides*, *Nothofagus fusca*, *Nothofagus menziesii*, *Nothofagus solandri*, *Nothofagus truncata*, *Larix decidua*, *Pinus contorta*, *Pinus monticola*, *Pinus mugo*, *Pinus muricata*, *Pinus nigra*, *Pinus patula*, *Pinus pinaster*, *Pinus ponderosa*, *Pinus radiata*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Pinus uncinata*, and *Pseudotsuga menziesii*

Taxonomic reference system: Taxonomy follows Kew Gardens Plants of the World Online (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>)

Ecological level: species

Data sources: Conifer occurrence records were downloaded from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). *Nothofagus* records came from the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA), the New Zealand Indigenous Carbon Monitoring System and our own fieldwork. All data, DOIs and accession details are provided in the Data Accessibility section of the manuscript or as Supporting Information

Sampling design: Observation records were downloaded from public databases as described above, except those from our own fieldwork which were from 81 *Nothofagus* forest plots spatially stratified across South Island, New Zealand

Sample size: Sample size for each species is provided in Table 2 of the manuscript

Clipping: *Nothofagus* species were modelled within New Zealand (their global range), but conifer species were modelled at the global level to include their full native and introduced ranges

Scaling: We performed geographical filtering of occurrence records to retain one record per 1 km² grid cell, and performed environmental filtering using the “*occfilt_env*” function from the “*flexsdm*” R package version 1.3.2 with 12 bins. This removed records with similar values across all environmental predictor variables. Further details are provided in the manuscript.

Cleaning: We cleaned the occurrence records with the R package “*CoordinateCleaner*” version 2.0-20, using default settings to remove a) records that were duplicates, b) those with equal latitude and longitude, c) pre-1970 records, d) those within a 10,000 m radius of country capitals, a 1,000 m radius of country centroids, a 1 degree radius of the GBIF headquarters, or a 100 m radius of known biodiversity institutions, e) those with a recorded spatial uncertainty of greater than 1 km, and f) those in the ocean.

Absence data: Not applicable

Background data: We used a target-group background approach by using known locations of species with similar life history strategies to constrain background sampling. For the background records, we used occurrence data downloaded from GBIF for a) a list of all native New Zealand woody plants for the *Nothofagus* models, and b) all Pinaceae species

for the conifer models. We cleaned background records and performed geographical and environmental filtering as described above for the species' occurrence records. For each model we used background points within a 500 km buffer of the species' occurrence records.

Errors and biases: All data were cleaned and filtered as described above to reduce bias and error as much as possible. However, it is possible that the data still contain misidentified records, or are missing records of some populations.

Data partitioning

Training data: Occurrence records that remained after filtering (described above) were used to train models

Validation data: Model validation was undertaken using the "ENMevaluate" function with the spatial block approach to partition occurrence and background data into four blocks (with the model built with three groups and evaluated on the fourth). Further details of this method can be found here: <https://jamiemkass.github.io/ENMeval/articles/ENMeval-2.0-vignette.html>

Predictor variables

Predictor variables: Maximum temperature of warmest month (°C), Minimum temperature of coldest month (°C), Mean temperature of warmest quarter (°C), Mean temperature of coldest quarter (°C), Precipitation of wettest month (kg m⁻²), Precipitation of driest month (kg m⁻²), Precipitation of wettest quarter (kg m⁻²), Precipitation of driest quarter (kg m⁻²), Soil pH (1-14), Concentration of soil carbon (%).

Data sources: Climate variables were downloaded from the CHELSA database version 2.1 (September 2022). Soil variables were downloaded from the New Zealand Land Resource Information Systems (LRIS) soil database (SMAP; <https://smap.landcareresearch.co.nz/>; September 2022).

Spatial extent: -180, 180, -90, 90 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 30 arc seconds for climate variables, 100 m² for soil variables.

Coordinate reference system: +proj=cea +lat_ts=30 +lon_0=0 +x_0=0 +y_0=0 +datum=WGS84 +units=m +no_defs

Temporal extent: Climate variables: average of 1981-2010; soil variables: predictions provided by SMAP (see above), collection date of underlying data is unknown

Data processing: All raster layers were reprojected to the Behrmann equal-area projection at 1 km² grid cell resolution using the "raster" R package version 3.5

Errors and biases: Unknown

Dimension reduction: For each of the five *Nothofagus* and 13 conifer models we calculated the variance inflation factor (VIF) values for the eight climate predictors and two soil

predictors (Nothofagus only) with the R package “SpatialRF” version 1.1.4. We retained variables with VIF values less than ten, resulting in either four or five variables selected as predictors for each species (see Table 2 of the manuscript).

Transfer data

Data sources: Climate variables were downloaded from the CHELSA database version 2.1 (September 2022) and were the average of 2041-2070 predictions.

Spatial extent: -180, 180, -90, 90 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 30 arc seconds

Temporal extent: 2041-2070

Temporal resolution: Average of 2041-2070 predictions

Models and scenarios: We selected future climate projections from two of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) that represent the best and worst case emissions scenarios; SSP126 and SSP585. We ran separate species distribution models using each SSP and each of three different Global Circulation Models (GCMs): GFDL-ESM4, MPI-ESM-1-2-HR, and IPSL-CM6A-1R. We generated consensus future predictions for each SSP by multiplying the binary outputs from the three GCMs.

Data processing: All raster layers were reprojected to the Behrmann equal-area projection at 1 km² grid cell resolution using the “raster” R package version 3.5

Quantification of Novelty: We created Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surface (MESS) maps to show areas where SDMs were extrapolating to conditions outside the range of model calibration

Model

Variable pre-selection

Variable pre-selection: The eight climate variables were chosen to represent temperature and precipitation extremes. Soil carbon and pH were chosen because these were the soil variables available in the SMAP database with good coverage across the full extent of New Zealand.

Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity: For each of the five Nothofagus and 13 conifer models we calculated the variance inflation factor (VIF) values for the eight climate predictors and two soil predictors (Nothofagus only) with the R package “SpatialRF” version 1.1.4. We retained variables with VIF values less than ten, resulting in either four or five variables selected as predictors for each species (see Table 2 of the manuscript).

Model settings

maxent: featureSet (Hinge), regularizationMultiplierSet (2)

Model settings (extrapolation): Models were allowed to extrapolate beyond the training range (clamp=FALSE)

Model estimates

Coefficients: Did not extract

Model selection - model averaging - ensembles

Model selection: We initially explored a range of regularisation multiplier settings (1, 2 or 3) and feature class settings (including linear, hinge, quadratic, and their interactions). Results were similar with all combinations of regularisation multiplier and feature class settings, so we followed Elith et al. (2010; <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2010.00036.x>) by using the regularisation multiplier of 2 and the hinge feature class for all models.

Analysis and Correction of non-independence

Spatial autocorrelation: We used spatial block cross-validation to calculate model performance statistics

Threshold selection

Threshold selection: To convert continuous outputs to binary range maps indicating suitable/unsuitable habitat, we used a threshold calculated to maximise the sum of sensitivity (true predicted presences) and specificity (true predicted absences). We calculated individual thresholds for each species by using the “ENMevaluate” function from the “ENMeval” package version 2.0.1 with four spatial blocks and a customised function (see R code provided as Supporting Information) that averaged the thresholds calculated for each spatial block using the “dismo” package version 1.3-9.

Assessment

Performance statistics

Performance on training data: AUC, ORMTP

Performance on validation data: pROC

Performance on test data: Not applicable

Plausibility check

Response shapes: We did not examine response plots

Expert judgement: All maps were examined to ensure that the predictions were reasonable estimates of the expected species' ranges

Prediction

Prediction output

Prediction unit: 1 km²

Post-processing: All predictions were clipped to the extent of New Zealand and transformed to the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) projection for the manuscript figures. All area statistics were calculated using the Behrmann equal-area projection. Rasters (.tif) are provided in the Behrmann equal-area projection at 1km² grid cell resolution, which is the projection in which the SDMs were performed.

Uncertainty quantification

Input data uncertainty: All input data were rigorously cleaned as described above; uncertainty of the remaining data could not be quantified

Scenario uncertainty: We provide Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surface (MESS) maps to show areas where SDMs were extrapolating to conditions outside the range of model calibration

Novel environments: Areas where the SDMs were extrapolating were not masked, but can be viewed in the MESS maps provided in Supporting Information